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Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

Study of Performance Appraisal System for Faculty Members in
Selected Management Institutes Affiliated to
Shivaji University Kolhapur

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An Autonomous Institute Under UGC & Shivaji University
College with Potential for Excellence (CPE) - III Phase.

How to cite this paper: Mr. Santosh V. Hasure | Mr. Viraj V. Jadhav "Study of Performance Appraisal System for Faculty Members in Selected Management Institutes Affiliated to Shivaji University Kolhapur" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Special Issue | Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through Interdisciplinary Practices in Management, March 2019, pp.76-81, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23069.pdf>

IJTSRD23069

ABSTRACT

Performance Appraisal provides a periodic review and evaluation of an individual's job performance. Although the appraisal forms may only be completed once a year, the job of performance appraisal is continuous – sometimes daily and requires effective communication on both the part of the supervisor and the Respondent. The supervisor is ultimately responsible to make sure these conversations actually take place and are documented. It is essential that the supervisor hold all performance discussions and documentation in complete confidence. Every organization is having an objective towards optimum performance and the Respondent is the key in achieving it. It is necessary that the Respondents performance should reach optimality for the success of the organization. Many organizations are having performance appraisal systems to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of their Respondent using linguistic labels to their performance. In a production unit, Respondent performance is proportional to the quality and quantity of production, where as in case of educational institute there is no such direct tool available to evaluate the productivity of its faculty members. In judging efficiency of faculty members, often the institute deals with vague or imprecise data resulting to an inconsistency performance evaluation. This study has been particularly taken by the researcher to understand the present scenario of the institute performance appraisal system in these colleges. Researcher wants to find out the weather appraisal is really helping Respondents for the better future or not.

KEYWORDS: Performance Appraisal, Academic performance Indicator, Appraiser

I. INTRODUCTION

Performance Appraisal provides a periodic review and evaluation of an individual's job performance. Although the appraisal forms may only be completed once a year, the job of performance appraisal is continuous – sometimes daily and requires effective communication on both the part of the supervisor and the Respondent. The supervisor is ultimately responsible to make sure these conversations actually take place and are documented.

It is essential that the supervisor hold all performance discussions and documentation in complete confidence. One Respondent's performance should never be discussed with

another Respondent. This action is one of the best ways for a supervisor to lose the trust of all Respondents. Every organization is having an objective towards optimum performance and the Respondent is the key in achieving it. It is necessary that the Respondents performance should reach optimality for the success of the organization. Many organizations are having performance appraisal systems to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of their Respondent using linguistic labels to their performance. In a production unit, Respondent performance is proportional to the quality and quantity of production, where as in case of educational institute there is no such direct tool available to evaluate the

productivity of its faculty members. In judging efficiency of faculty members, often the institute deals with vague or imprecise data resulting to an inconsistency performance evaluation.

The subject of performance appraisal appears a major subject of controversy in management circles. According to Kurt (2004), while business leaders see the need for appraisal systems, they are frequently disappointed in them because of various challenges that derail its objectives. One of the responsibilities of management is to ensure that an organization functions effectively and efficiently. In order to achieve these goals, managers must be able to determine and assess performance levels of both an organization and its individual Respondents (Kurt, 2004).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. Anup Kumar Ghosh, Debmallya Chatterji, Biswamp Ghosh (2010)

Every organization is having an objective towards optimum performance and the employees are the key in achieving that. It is necessary that the employees' performance should reach optimality for the success of the organization. Many organizations are having performance appraisal system to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of their employees using linguistic labels to their performance. Adu, Cecilia Adurayemi in his article "Cashless Policy and Its Effects on The Nigerian Economy" discussed the effects of cashless policy on the Nigerian economy

2. **Forrest Flaniken, (2011)** It is helpful to briefly consider some of the issues related to faculty appraisal because faculty appraisal has had an influence on the acceptance and use of performance appraisal of staff at colleges and universities. The appraisal of faculty has a lengthy history, unlike the appraisal of staff which is relatively brief, but there has always been a degree of controversy that has surrounded it (Braskamp & Ory, 1994).

3. Gangan Prathap and K. Ratnavelu (September 2015)

We carried out a research performance analysis of leading higher education institutions in Malaysia using bibliometric data from the latest (2014) release of the Scimago Institutions Rankings (SIR). We tracked the complete performance chain: input-output-excellence-outcome-productivity using indicators that represent quantity, quality and productivity dimensions Olalekan S. Akinola highlighted the negative side of cashless economy in his paper "Cashless Society, Problems and Prospects, Data Mining Research Potentials". According to author, there are major negative implications with a cashless society such as privacy issues and losing the liberty of cash. One of the main issues regarding the implementation of a smart card/chip that would record and control all financial transactions electronically is the assault on privacy.

4. **Nuwagaba Fredie (May 2016)** The study set out to assess the factors affecting implementation of the performance appraisal system at Nyamasheeke District Local Government (NDLG), Rwanda. The study was based on these objectives; To Examine how management processes affects the implementation of the performance appraisal in Nyamasheeke District Local Government, Investigating how the level of trust between the

appraiser and appraisee affects implementation of performance appraisal, to study how communication between the appraisee and appraiser affects the implementation of performance appraisal and lastly to examine how training levels of appraisees affect the implementation of performance appraisal in Nyamasheeke District Local Government. Mamta, Prof. Hariom Tyagi, Dr. Abhishek Shukla in their paper "The Study of Electronic Payment Systems" have identified the issues and challenges of electronic payment systems and offered some solutions to improve the e-payment system quality. Researchers states that Electronic payment refers to the mode of payment which does not include physical cash or cheque. The successful implementations of electronic payment systems depends on how the security and privacy dimensions perceived by consumers as well as sellers are popularly managed, in turn would improve the market confidence in the system.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To identify the criteria in measuring faculty performance in selected management institutes affiliated to Shivaji University Kolhapur.
2. To study the satisfaction levels of faculties about performance Appraisal systems in selected management institutes under study

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The type of research method used for this research is Descriptive Research. Both primary and secondary data has collected for the completion of this project. In order to achieve the objective of study required information has collected through following procedure.

SAMPLING DESIGN

The present study has carried out in selected post graduate management institute affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur which covers Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara districts. There are 24 management institutes covered in the study. Researcher has selected the CENSUS POPULATION for the present study. To select the respondents from the institute researcher has selected all permanent respondents from all the institutes..

V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

1. Important Factors Consider While Appraising The Performance of Respondent

While appraising the performance of the Respondents what factors which considered by the institutes is very much important. So to understand in this the researcher is interested to find out the important factors that institutes is considering while appraising the Respondents in the institutes. For that researcher wants to understand the opinion of the respondent about important factors that institutes is considering while appraising the Respondents performance.

Here the researcher has mentioned the thirteen important factors and respondents are asked to give their opinion about the important factor considering while appraising the Respondents performance that done by the institutes. The responses is taken on five point likert scale 5 - Very Important, 4 - Moderately Important, 3- Neutral, 2 - Slightly Important, 1 - Low Importance.

Table No. 5.1: Important Factors Consider While Appraising The Performance of Respondent

Level Of Importance →	Factor ↓		Very Important	Moderately Important	Neutral	Slightly Important	Less Important	Total
Subject Knowledge	F		65	10	9	3	1	88
	P		73.9	11.4	10.2	3.4	1.1	100
Qualification	F		30	49	8	1	0	88
	P		34.1	55.7	9.1	1.1	0	100
Experiences	F		49	17	15	5	2	88
	P		55.7	19.3	17.0	5.7	2.3	100
Feedback from students	F		26	50	6	6	0	88
	P		29.5	56.8	6.8	6.8	0	100
Appearances and Personality	F		40	31	10	4	3	88
	P		45.5	35.2	11.4	4.5	3.4	100
Relationship with other faculties	F		47	27	8	5	1	88
	P		53.4	30.7	9.1	5.7	1.1	100
Relationship with authorities	F		28	50	10	0	0	88
	P		31.8	56.8	11.4	0	0	100
Guest Lectures conducted	F		35	31	14	8	0	88
	P		39.8	35.2	15.9	9.1	0	100
Workshops, Seminars, Conferences conducted / attended	F		26	49	11	1	1	88
	P		29.5	55.7	12.5	1.1	1.1	100
Research Publications	F		41	29	16	2	0	88
	P		46.6	33.0	18.2	2.3	0	100
Cooperative Nature	F		34	40	14	0	0	88
	P		38.6	45.5	15.9	0	0	100
Character of concerned faculty	F		42	34	7	5	0	88
	P		47.7	38.6	8.0	5.7	0	100
Initiative in performing task	F		35	34	15	3	1	88
	P		39.8	38.6	17.0	3.4	1.1	100

Important Factors Consider While Appraising The Performance of employee

Graph No. 01 Important Factors Consider While Appraising The Performance of Respondent

The above frequency table & graph shows that the opinion of the respondent's important factors considered while appraising the performance of the Respondents that is done by the institutes. It has been taken through the scale of level of importance towards each factor listed mentioned.

As per subject knowledge concern 73.9 % respondent said that subject knowledge is very important while appraising the performance of the Respondent, then 11.4 % respondents said that subject knowledge is moderately important, 10.2% respondents are neutral on it, then 3.4% respondents said it is slightly important and only 1.1 % respondents said it is less important while appraising the performance.

Table No. 5.2: Descriptive Analysis For Important Factors Consider While Appraising The Performance of Respondent

Sr. No.	Important Factor For The Performance Appraisal System	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Mean Rank
1	Subject Knowledge	4.5	0.896	1
2	Qualification	4.2	0.656	3
3	Experiences	4.2	1.063	3
4	Feedback from students	4.1	0.797	4
5	Appearances and Personality	4.1	1.023	4
6	Relationship with other faculties	4.3	0.937	2
7	Relationship with authorities	4.2	0.628	3
8	Guest Lectures conducted	4.1	0.963	4
9	Workshops, Seminars, Conferences conducted / attended	4.1	0.749	4
10	Research Publications	4.3	0.816	2
11	Cooperative Nature	4.2	0.707	3
12	Character of concerned faculty	4.3	0.843	2
13	Initiative in performing task	4.1	0.895	4

The above analysis indicates that the most important factors while appraising the Respondents in the post graduate management institutes under Shivaji University are Subject Knowledge, Research Publications and Relationship, Qualification, Experiences, Relationship with authorities, Cooperative Nature with other faculties with the high mean score. Along with that other factors are also important like Feedback from students, Appearances and Personality, Guest Lectures conducted, Workshops, Seminars, Conferences conducted / attended and Initiative in performing task but less preference given by the respondent while appraising the performance of Respondents.

2. Opinion About Present Performance Appraisal System Used By Institute

"Performance appraisal" is a discrete, formal, organizationally sanctioned event, usually not occurring more frequently than once or twice a year, which has clearly stated performance dimensions and/or criteria that are used in the evaluation process. Furthermore, it is an evaluation process, in that quantitative scores are often assigned based on the judged level of the Respondent's job performance on the dimensions or criteria used, and the scores are shared with the Respondent being evaluated.

Table No. 5.3: Opinion about Present Performance Appraisal System Used By Institute

Level of Agreeableness →	Statement ↓		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
	Satisfied with existing performance appraisal system	F	48	32	7	1	0	88
		P	54.5	36.4	8.0	1.1	0	100
	Management fixes pay scale through the performance rating	F	22	48	13	5	0	88
		P	25.0	54.5	14.8	5.7	0	100
	Good sponsorship for faculty for participation in FDP's, Seminars, Conferences, Refresher Courses given by our institute	F	42	22	16	8	0	88
		P	47.7	25.0	18.2	9.1	0	100
	Impartial Appraisal policy for performance of faculty is adopted by our institute	F	28	42	16	2	0	88
		P	31.8	47.7	18.2	2.3	0	100
	Transfer, demotion, suspension and dismissal is based on performance appraisal	F	29	22	32	5	0	88
		P	33.0	25.0	36.4	5.7	0	100
	Appraisal system monitors major strong points and weakness of work	F	20	45	17	4	2	88
		P	22.7	51.1	19.3	4.5	2.3	100
	Impartial appraisal system gives motivation to faculty in our institute	F	40	30	17	0	1	88
		P	45.5	34.1	19.3	0	1.1	100
	Our institute's performance appraisal systems gives clear cut ideas to faculties about what is expected from them by management	F	31	41	16	0	0	88
		P	35.2	46.6	18.2	0	0	100

By using performance appraisal system, management clearly understands the needs of faculties	F	35	37	11	5	0	88
	P	39.8	42.0	12.5	5.7	0	100
The appraisal system provides an opportunity for self-review and reflection	F	44	39	3	2	0	88
	P	50.0	44.3	3.4	2.3	0	100
Periodic orientation programs are conducted to explain the objective and other details of appraisal system	F	26	36	20	4	2	88
	P	29.5	40.9	22.7	4.5	2.3	100
The appraisal data are used as inputs for recognition and encouragement for high performers.	F	26	36	20	4	2	88
	P	29.5	40.9	22.7	4.5	2.3	100
Whether management gives you sufficient time to bring improvement in your day to day official activity.	P	36	34	14	3	1	88
	F	40.9	38.6	15.9	3.4	1.1	100

**F: Frequency P: Percentage
Opinion About Present Performance Appraisal System Used
By Institute**

Graph No. 5.2: Opinion about Present Performance Appraisal System Used By Institute

The above frequency table & graph shows that the opinion of the respondent's about appraising the performance of the Respondents that is done by the institutes.

As per Satisfied with existing performance appraisal system concern 54.5 % respondent said that they are strongly agree about this statement, then 36.4 % respondents said that they are agree about this statement, 8% respondents are neither nor disagree about this statement, then 1.1 % respondents said that they are disagree about this statement and only no respondents said that they are strongly disagree about this statement.

From the above analysis it is clear that from all the statements Satisfied with existing performance appraisal system Good sponsorship for faculty for participation in FDP's, Seminars, Conferences, Refresher Courses given by our institute, Our institute's performance appraisal systems gives clear cut ideas to faculties about what is expected from them by management, The appraisal system provides an opportunity for self-review and reflection on which Respondents are strongly agreed than other things about performance appraisal system.

VI. CONCLUSION

From the study findings and base on the objectives of the study, it can be concluded that Respondent opinion is independent on Respondent gender but it is dependent on Respondents designation and academic qualification, Subject Knowledge, Character of concerned faculty, Qualification, Experiences, Feedback from students, Cooperative Nature, Relationship with authorities are the reasons for the better appraisal.

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